

The Indonesian version of volunteer functions inventory: Its validity and reliability

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ABSTRACT

The volunteer function inventory (VFI) is an assessment tool to measure individual volunteer motivation. VFI measures individual motivation to volunteer by examining the functional motives of each volunteer. This research aimed to adapt the VFI to the Indonesian language. VFI consists of 30 items divided into five dimensions. This study utilized a non-experimental quantitative research method. Samples were acquired by accidental random sampling with $N = 176$. In this study, reliability testing was carried out with items and dimensions of Cronbach's α . Validity tests were examined using construct validity and item analysis. The results of the Indonesian version of VFI showed high reliability and validity. Besides, the item analysis also shows that the quality of each item is excellent. The Indonesian version of VFI will be suitable for various education fields in Indonesia to measure the students' voluntary willingness in community development activities, for example, in measuring the impact of volunteerism in the Merdeka Belajar Kampus Merdeka (MBKM) social activities and other activities within the communities.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A volunteer is someone who provides services without expecting anything in return [1]. Volunteer activities are challenging since individuals may prefer to focus on profit, especially financially. However, volunteering is nothing new and trending nowadays. Many activities that accept volunteers have made many people more enthusiastic about volunteering. This volunteer spirit has been driven by cultural values, principles, ideology, and traditions which have indirectly increased the confidence and courage of the volunteers. In 2022, there have been various regional and global sports activities that have absorbed thousands of volunteers. The FIFA World Cup Qatar 2022 accepted up to 20,000 volunteer candidates, who were assessed via Volunteer.FIFA.com [2]. Youth involvement in the community sport showed their volunteerisms [3]. At the Sea Games event held in Malaysia, in 2017, the committee only received around 1,500 volunteers out of more than 10,000 registrants [4]. In addition to volunteers for event activities, there are also volunteers in social activities, such as volunteers who came to help handle the earthquake in Palu [5]. During the COVID-19 period, there was also volunteer training for up to almost 1,000 participants related to health and medicine [6]. The difference between the types of volunteers can affect the motivation of volunteers who register. In types of volunteer events such as music or sports events, volunteers expect benefits to be offered, such as getting extensive relationships, improving soft skills and hard skills, and including them in a curriculum vitae [7]. As

for social, some can make it easier to register for similar jobs, such as community service in education or health, but the majority are because they have enough empathy to help others [1], [8].

Measuring motivation in volunteers has used a variety of methods, both quantitatively, and qualitatively. Some use quantitative questionnaires such as the volunteer function inventory (VFI) [9], which measures motivation to volunteer by examining the functional motives of each individual who chooses to volunteer. The attitude toward helping others scale, a measuring tool to measure helping behavior, was defined by the author as a global evaluation of helping behavior [10]. The helping attitude scale measures beliefs, feelings, and behaviors associated with helping behavior [11]. Bales volunteerism-activism scale measures primary motivation in acting as a volunteer [12]. Helping power motivation measures a person's motivation to help others [13]. In Indonesia, there was research by Rahmawati *et al.* [14] regarding the relationship between satisfaction, motivation, and commitment in volunteer participation in East Kalimantan. This study utilized a measuring tool similar to VFI [14]. In addition, previous research aimed to look at the involvement and commitment of young people in multicultural communities [15]. Tools that precisely measure volunteers in the Indonesian language are still lacking.

Clary *et al.* [9] conducted the reliability and validity tests in the original VFI measurement tool. This original VFI study's reliability test was a test-retest within one month, with reliable results obtained. The validity test utilized the construct validity test, which looks at the correlation between the VFI and the satisfaction measurement tool in volunteers [9]. These tests showed that the measuring instrument could measure motivation in doing voluntary work and was reliable because it was consistent within one month for the same individuals [9]. A study was conducted in Indonesia using the VFI measurement tool, but no adaptation, validity, or reliability was reported [14]. Measurements regarding volunteering still need to be improved. Today's measurements are still common, such as measurements of helping behavior or in psychological studies such as psychosocial [16], [17].

Volunteer activities are now increasing, and dissemination of information is also easier for both those who register and those who receive volunteers. As mentioned earlier, there are various volunteer activities, such as regional and global sports activities to volunteering for disaster relief. There is quite a lot of research and measurement instruments to measure individual behavior in volunteers globally. However, their usage still needs to improve, especially for their usage and adaptation in Indonesia. This research aims to adapt the VFI measurement tool to the Indonesian language and determine its validity and reliability.

2. METHOD

VFI is a tool to measure motivation in doing voluntary activities [9]. Adapting VFI to the Indonesian language is necessary because the Indonesian language is Indonesia's national and primary language. The adaptation of this VFI utilized a non-experimental quantitative research method due to the absence of treatment of participants and the resulting data in the form of numbers [9]. This measuring instrument consists of 30 items to determine the individual motivation for volunteer activities. In this measuring instrument, individuals were required to make a personal assessment by filling out a response scale from 1 (not important or not accurate) to 7 (very important or accurate).

In adapting this measurement tool, the researchers first translated the VFI into the Indonesian language (forward translation). Furthermore, linguists proofread, validated, and re-translated the VFI translation into English. The final translation results were transformed into an online form accompanied by informed consent. The questionnaire was then distributed online via the Google Form platform. The results of VFI data in spreadsheet form were then analyzed using JASP 0.15.0.0 software.

Sampling for the Indonesian language VFI adaptation was the accidental random sampling method. The accidental random sampling method was utilized to conduct the sampling process for adapting the Indonesian language VFI. Accidental sampling refers to the researchers incidentally encountering respondents and selecting them as samples, with the data being used if they are deemed appropriate [18]. The sample in this study included 121 college students, 24 senior high school/vocational high school students, 19 employees, and 12 entrepreneurs. Of the total participants, 158 of them had participated in volunteer activities, and 18 participants had never participated in volunteer activities (N total = 176).

We tested the reliability and validity of the VFI Indonesian version. We utilized Cronbach's α items and split half items to test the reliability. Each item on the measuring instrument measures the same thing as Cronbach's α , and the split half dimension can see the suitability of each dimension in this measuring instrument [19]. The validity was tested using the construct validity method by looking at the correlation between each item and the total number to see whether each item has a valid value. As well as item analysis is also carried out to see the quality of each item.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 presented the general description of the participants in terms of gender, age, and occupation. We conducted an item analysis to see if any items had poor quality. According to Shultz *et al.* [20], an item can be good if it has an item-rest correlation value > 0.3 . Table 2 shows the analysis results of all items and the item-rest correlation score, all of which are good quality. Based on the results, all the Indonesian VFI items are of good quality.

Table 1. Respondent descriptive statistic (N=176)

Participant		N
Gender	Male	47
	Female	129
Age	17 - 23	140
	23 - 30	10
	30 - 40	13
	> 40	13
Profession	Employee	19
	College student	121
	High school student	24
	Entrepreneur	12

Table 2. Item analysis

Item number (dimension)	Item-rest correlation	Item number (dimension)	Item-rest correlation
1 (CA)	0.714	16 (VA)	0.857
2 (SO)	0.67	17 (SO)	0.795
3 (VA)	0.748	18 (UN)	0.859
4 (SO)	0.722	19 (VA)	0.826
5 (EN)	0.803	20 (PR)	0.759
6 (SO)	0.759	21 (CA)	0.809
7 (PR)	0.785	22 (VA)	0.855
8 (VA)	0.862	23 (SO)	0.771
9 (PR)	0.832	24 (PR)	0.674
10 (CA)	0.873	25 (UN)	0.832
11 (PR)	0.793	26 (EN)	0.797
12 (UN)	0.85	27 (EN)	0.84
13 (EN)	0.829	28 (CA)	0.807
14 (UN)	0.86	29 (EN)	0.823
15 (CA)	0.895	30 (UN)	0.849

Table 3 shows a reliability test using the split-half dimension method. The result showed that the reliability coefficient of the split-half dimension was 0.944, which showed the internal consistency coefficient with a content sampling error of 0.056. Referring to the reliability coefficient according to Shultz *et al.* [20], the score on split-half 1 will produce a score consistent with split-half 2. Therefore, the Indonesian VFI is reliable.

Table 3. Dimension split half reliability

Test category	Pearson's r	p
Split half 1-split half 2	0.944	< 0.001

Additionally, the reliability test with Cronbach's alpha method resulted in the reliability coefficient of Cronbach's alpha as 0.983, with an internal consistency coefficient with a content sampling error of 0.017. Referring to the reliability coefficient, according to Shultz *et al.* [20], each item in the Indonesian VFI will produce consistent scores. We also conducted a reliability test on the six dimensions of the Indonesian VFI. Table 4 shows the results of the six dimensions' Cronbach's alpha. We concluded that all six dimensions showed the minimum value of good reliability, namely 0.70. Therefore, the Indonesian VFI can be concluded as a reliable measurement tool.

Table 5 shows the results of the construct validity test with a p-value < 0.001 . All Indonesian VFI items in Table 5 shows that $p < 0.001$. Referring to Shultz *et al.* [20], a validity with a p-value < 0.05 showed valid results. Therefore, the Indonesian VFI is a valid measurement tool. The Indonesian VFI adaptation test results showed good quality items so that all 30 items could be maintained as shown in Table 2. The reliability and validity tests proved that the Indonesian VFI is a reliable and valid measurement tool to measure individual

motivation to carry out voluntary activities. Therefore the Indonesian VFI can be utilized to assess volunteers' motivation.

Table 4. The six dimensions' Cronbach's α reliability

Dimension	Cronbach's α
Total protective dimension	0.868
Total value dimension	0.924
Total career dimension	0.929
Total social dimension	0.853
Total understanding dimension	0.909
Total enhancement dimension	0.914

Table 5. Construct validity

Item number-total	Pearson's r	p	Item number-total	Pearson's r	p
1	0.735	< 0.001	16	0.867	< 0.001
2	0.691	< 0.001	17	0.809	< 0.001
3	0.767	< 0.001	18	0.869	< 0.001
4	0.741	< 0.001	19	0.838	< 0.001
5	0.818	< 0.001	20	0.776	< 0.001
6	0.776	< 0.001	21	0.823	< 0.001
7	0.802	< 0.001	22	0.865	< 0.001
8	0.872	< 0.001	23	0.787	< 0.001
9	0.844	< 0.001	24	0.700	< 0.001
10	0.883	< 0.001	25	0.844	< 0.001
11	0.808	< 0.001	26	0.811	< 0.001
12	0.861	< 0.001	27	0.851	< 0.001
13	0.842	< 0.001	28	0.821	< 0.001
14	0.870	< 0.001	29	0.835	< 0.001
15	0.903	< 0.001	30	0.860	< 0.001

The tests for adapting the VFI into Indonesian showed valid and reliable results. The item analysis test-correlation results for each item have a score of more than 0.60, which means that each item in the VFI adaptation has excellent quality. The item reliability test using Cronbach's alpha method has a score of 0.983, which meets the minimum standard score of 0.7, referring to Shultz *et al.* [20]. These results align with research by Brayley *et al.* [21], where all items have good quality and reliability. The reliability test results for each dimension of VFI adaptation also show reliable results with Cronbach's alpha dimension reliability test 0.969 and the split-half dimension reliability test 0.944; $p > 0.001$. These results are consistent with the results of a study conducted by Chacón *et al.* [22], which showed good reliability for each dimension with scores above 0.80. The validity test also shows valid results with a p -value < 0.001 , which is in line with research results [23]. The VFI adaptation to dutch also showed reliable results with all items above 0.7, test-correlation items ranging from 0.46 to 0.75, and good validity results, namely $p < 0.001$ [19]. VFI adaptation was also carried out in Iran [24] for members of the Iranian red crescent society youth organization. The reliability and validity results also met the standards.

Previous research in East Kalimantan, Indonesia, has used VFI to measure participants' motivation [14]. The study aimed to determine the relationship between motivation, satisfaction, and organizational commitment. This study's results revealed that volunteers with high motivation would also have high satisfaction with the organization; this would lead to a commitment to the organization [14]. Another VFI research showed the relationship between motivation and volunteer satisfaction in an art organization. This study's results revealed that of all VFI dimensions, three dimensions (career, understanding, and enhancement) had a significant relationship to volunteer satisfaction [25]. Another study was conducted by Intan and Sitio [26] to find out volunteer motivation in civil society organizations (CSO). The study found that four dimensions influenced the motivation of the volunteers, namely career, enhancement, protective, and social. All of these studies have used VFI, but there was no evidence of adaptation of VFI into the Indonesian language. Research by Niebuur *et al.* [27] was conducted to see the validation of the VFI adaptation into Dutch in an older generation population; the results obtained were in line with research results which showed good validity and reliability. The translation results were then used in other studies to compare volunteer motivation in volunteers and non-volunteers, which showed that the items in VFI led to different interpretations in the volunteer and non-volunteer groups. However, the results of both groups remained valid and reliable [27].

Merdeka Belajar Kampus Merdeka (MBKM) program is a mode of independent higher education learning designed to create a non-restrictive, creative learning community that meets the needs of students [28].

MBKM is one of the policies the Indonesian government implements for higher education in the country. With the MBKM program, the government gives freedom to educational institutions, especially students, in choosing their preferred field, thereby expanding scientific capital, and student expertise as preparation for entering the world of work [29]. The aim of implementing MBKM is to create highly competitive human beings following Pancasila values and prepare students to enter the world of work by increasing soft skills and hard skills relevant to the needs of the times [30]. The MBKM program is divided into 8 types of activities that students can choose, namely; i) internships/industry practices in the form of direct practical activities in the industrial world such as organizations or companies, ii) village projects in the form of activities that help villagers to building infrastructure and providing support for village development, iii) student exchanges in the form of taking semesters at other universities, iv) research, v) entrepreneurship in the form of independent business development with proof of proposals and proof of sales transactions, vi) independent studies/projects in the form of developing projects with unique topics that occur in society, vii) humanitarian projects in the form of developing humanitarian projects and can be carried out with social humanitarian institutions, and viii) teaching in schools in the form of student activities to educate or guide students in elementary schools, junior high schools, and high schools [28]. The implementation of MBKM in tertiary institutions received a lot of positive responses from students as well as lecturers. Even so, several obstacles arose, such as difficulties related to obtaining and lack of expansion, obstacles in collaboration between study programs and universities in exchange of lessons, problems in adaptation curriculum, teacher and student quality that needs to be improved, collaboration mechanisms that are still limited, difficulties in determining student interest, program selection by students [31]. Using the Indonesian VFI as an assessment can help students and lecturers determine specializations and see students' motivation toward social projects (programs 2, 5, 6, and 7) as parts of MBKM. Using the Indonesian VFI can make it easier for lecturers to guide students in choosing and implementing activities in the community through an MBKM program.

Our research limitation is in sampling. Most respondents (79%) were in the age range of 17-23 years. In contrast, the oldest respondent was 40 years old. The gap in the age range could affect the results of the research. In addition, there was also a gap in the respondent's profession. College students comprised the majority of respondents (68%), which can also affect the research. This condition might influence a career dimension in the VFI. Respondents in this study were also limited to cultural variations, ages, majors, and professions, which can affect research results [32]. Possible influence comes from non-volunteer respondents, which may have different interpretations, as in the study of Niebuur *et al.* [27], who examined the differences between non-volunteer groups and volunteer groups in the Netherlands. The result was that the non-volunteer and volunteer groups had different understandings of the VFI questionnaire items.

4. CONCLUSION

We successfully adapted the VFI to the Indonesian language. We found that the Indonesian VFI is valid and reliable in measuring the volunteers' motivation. The Indonesian VFI is valid because the measurement construct had good correlation values ($p < 0.001$). Thus, it can be used to see volunteer motivation in each individual. Indonesian VFI is reliable because the data proves this construct is consistent for each item and each dimension. Cronbach alpha is > 0.70 for all the items. This VFI adaptation can be implemented in education, such as in the MBKM program, especially those related to social projects. Future research applying the Indonesian VFI would give insights into volunteerism in Indonesia.

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